

Statistics and Trends in Higher Education in India: Growth and Challenges

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Abstract:

The higher education system in India has grown in a remarkable way, particularly in the post-independence period, to become one of the largest system of its kind in the world. However, the system has many issues of concern at present, like financing and management including access, equity and relevance, reorientation of programmes by laying emphasis on health consciousness, values and ethics and quality of higher education together with the assessment of institutions and their accreditation. These issues are important for the country, as it is now engaged in the use of higher education as a powerful tool to build a knowledge-based information society of the 21st Century. The higher education sphere in India grapples with a complex interplay of regulations, evolving developmental trends, and substantial challenges. Within regulations, pivotal policies like the National Education Policy, rules for foreign universities, and the National Research Foundation take centre stage. The rise of transformative technologies like AI also requires charting new developmental paths. The All-India Survey of Higher Education (AISHE) is the main source of comprehensive statistics on the higher education scenario in the country. The All-India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) was initiated in 2011, during which data for the year 2010-11 was collected. This Survey was necessitated as none of the source of data on higher education was giving complete picture of higher education in the country. The Survey intended to cover all the Institutions in the country engaged in imparting higher education. For the first time all the major Stakeholders in higher education, such as University Grants Commission, All India Council for Technical Education, Medical Council of India as well as State Governments participated in the data collection exercise. The current study aims to highlight the statistics, trends, growth and challenges in higher education system in India.

Keywords: Higher education, India, Challenges, Colleges, Universities, Statistics.

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1. Introduction

Education in India is provided by the public sector as well as the private sector, with control and funding coming from three levels: central, state and local. Under various articles of the Indian Constitution, free and compulsory education is provided as a fundamental right to children between the ages of 6 and 14.

The higher education system in India grew rapidly after independence and this system has expanded rapidly over the past two decades. This growth has been mainly driven by private sector initiatives. By 1980, there were 132 universities and 4738 colleges in the country enrolling around five percent of the eligible age group in higher education.

Today, India's higher education system is the world's third largest in terms of students, next to China and the United States. Unlike China, however, India has the advantage of English being the primary language of higher education and research. India educates approximately 11 per cent of its youth in higher education as compared to 20 per cent in China. The main governing body at the tertiary level is the University Grants Commission (India), which enforces its standards, advises the government, and helps coordinate between the centre and the state. Universities and its constituent colleges are the main institutes of higher education in India.

2. Objective of Study:

The main objectives of the study are-

1. To study the existing growth of higher education in India.
2. To study the growth in number of higher educational institutions.
3. To examine the growth in student enrolment of higher educational institutions
4. To evaluate the challenges in higher education in India.

3. Research Methodology:

The Researchers used an exploratory research technique based on past literature from respective journals, annual reports, newspapers and magazines covering wide collection of academic literature on All-India Survey of Higher Education (AISHE). Relevant secondary information has been collected from All India Survey on Higher Education 2015-16, 2019-20, 2020-21, 2021-22, Government of India, Ministry of Education, Department of Higher Education, Annual Status of Higher Education (ASHE), 2023 (<http://aishe.gov.in>). According to the objectives of the study, the research design is of descriptive in nature. Available secondary data was extensively used for the study.

4. Growth of Higher Education in India:

The Indian higher education system is one of the largest such systems in the World. There will be a tremendous pressure of numbers on this system and a large number of additional students will be knocking at the doors of higher education institutions in the country. There are also new challenges of management and regulation being faced by these institutions, which require serious attention, both at the institutions in the public sector and also those in the private sector now growing at a fast pace. As a result, the old structures of management established in pre-independent India and working during most of the twentieth century are now required to undergo drastic changes. Besides, the demands of the society for equity and accommodation cannot be neglected any more.

Today, while in terms enrolment, India is the third largest higher education system in the world (after China and the USA) with 45473 institutions and 1168 universities (AISHE:2021-22) and is the largest higher education system in the world in terms of number of institutions. There are different types of universities and colleges in the higher education system in the country. They vary terms of their academic, administrative and financial arrangements. Universities can either be established by an Act of Parliament or by the state legislatures. Those established by the Act of Parliament are the central universities and the ones set up by the state legislatures are state universities. Some higher education institutions are granted the 'deemed university' status by the central government through gazette notifications. A few institutions are established by the Parliament / state legislatures as institutions of national importance. Universities, deemed universities and institutions of national importance are degree-granting institutions.

5. Growth in Number of Higher Educational Institutions:

The number of universities and similar institutions listed on AISHE (All India Survey on

Higher Education) portal has increased from 621 in 2010-11 to 1168 in 2021-22 by almost 88% as shown in the Table No. I. Whereas the number of colleges has increased from 32,974 in 2010-11 to 45,473 in 2021-22 by about 38% as shown in the table number: I

Table No. I: Number of Universities/Colleges

Institution	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2020-21	2021-22
University	621	642	667	723	760	799	1,113	1168
College	32974	34852	35525	36634	38498	39071	43,796	45473

Sources: Ministry of HRD, Department of Higher Education, 2016, GOI and Ministry of Education , All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) 2020,2021 2022

During 2021-22, 1168 universities listed on AISHE. The type- wise details of the 1168 universities are given below in table number: II.

Table No. II: Number of Universities during 2015- 2016, 2019-20, 2020-21, 2021-22

Type of university	Number of Universities			
	2015-16	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22
Central Open University	1	1	1	1
Central University	43	48	51	53
Deemed University- Government	32	36	34	33
Institution Under State Legislature Act	5	5	5	6
Institution of National Importance	75	135	149	153
Deemed University- Private	79	80	80	81
State Private University	197	327	365	391
State Open University	13	14	14	16
State Public University	329	386	403	423
State Private Open University	1	1	1	1
Deemed University- Government Aided	11	10	10	10
Others	13	-----	-----	-----
Grand Total	799	1043	1113	1168

Sources: Ministry of HRD, Department of Higher Education, 2016, 2020, 2021, 2022, GOI.

Among 1168 Universities, 473 universities are privately managed and 467 Universities have adopted villages under Unnat Bharat Programme. 17 universities are exclusively for women with 4 in Rajasthan, 2 in Tamil Nadu, 1 each in Andhra Pradesh, Assam, New Delhi, Haryana, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Odisha, Uttarakhand and West Bengal. There are 328 affiliating universities.

The Ministry of Education, Government of India has released All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) 2020-2021. The Ministry has been conducting All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) since 2011, covering all higher educational institutions located in Indian Territory and imparting higher education in the country. The survey collects detailed information on different parameters such as student enrolment, teacher’s data, infrastructural information, financial information etc. For the first time, in AISHE 2020-21, HEIs have filled data using entirely online data collection platform through the Web Data Capture Format (DCF) developed by Department of Higher Education through the National Informatics Centre (NIC).

Table No. III: Number of Universities (as of 14, 2023)

Type of university	Number of Universities
Central University	56
Deemed University	124
Private University	455
State University	478
Grand Total	1,113

Sources: Ministry of HRD, Department of Higher Education, 2023, GOI.

During 2021-22, the number of universities has increased by 55, and the number of Colleges has increased by 2648. 191 new Higher Education Institutions have been established in North Eastern States since 2014-15. Highest number of universities is in Rajasthan (92), Uttar Pradesh (84) and Gujarat (83). 17 universities (of which 14 are State Public) and 4,375 Colleges are exclusively for women. States with Highest college density:

Karnataka (62), Telangana (53), Kerala (50), Himachal Pradesh (50), Andhra Pradesh (49), Uttarakhand (40), Rajasthan (40), Tamilnadu (40). 43% universities and 61.4% colleges are located in Rural areas.

Evidently, the increase in State Private and State Public Universities are very high as shown below in Table Number: IV.

Table No. IV: Number of State Private and State Public Universities

University Type	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2019-20	2021-22
State Public University	281	286	292	309	316	329	386	423
State Private University	87	105	122	153	181	197	327	391
Deemed University Private	91	90	91	91	90	90	80	81
Institute of National Importance	59	59	62	68	75	75	135	153
Central University	41	42	42	42	43	43	48	53
Deemed University Government	40	38	36	36	32	32	36	33

Sources: Ministry of HRD, Department of Higher Education, 2016, 2020, 2022, GOI.

Uttar Pradesh has maximum number of colleges (8375), followed by Maharashtra (4692), Karnataka (4430), Rajasthan (3934), Tamil Nadu (2829), Madhya Pradesh (2742), Andhra Pradesh (2602), Gujarat (2395), Telangana (2083) and West Bengal (1514).

6. Growth in Student Enrolment of Higher Educational Institutions:

In the higher educational institutions in India the enrolment has grown considerably during the last 10 years, which has increased from 2,91,84,331 in 2011-12 to 4,32,68,181 in 2021-22. The overall growth is 48%. The growth in enrolment is shown in the table number: V.

Table No. V: Student Enrolment

Year	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22
Student Enrolment (in millions)	29.18	30.15	32.34	34.21	34.60	36.60	37.40	38.55	41.38	43.30

Sources: Ministry of HRD, Department of Higher Education, 2016, 2020, 2021, 2022 GOI.

In 2021-22, highest share of foreign students is from Nepal (28%), followed by Afghanistan (6.7%), United States (6.2%), Bangladesh (5.6%), UAE (4.9%), and Bhutan (3.3%). Top 10 countries constitute 64.7% of the total foreign students.

Enrolment at all the levels has increased over the years. During the last 10 years, which has increased from 2,91,84,331 in 2011-12 to 4,34,18,390 in 2021-22. The overall growth is 49%. The growth in enrolment shown below in table number: VI.

Table No. VI: Student Enrolment (at all levels)

Year	Student Enrolment								
	Ph.D.	M.Phil.	Post Graduate	Under Graduate	PG Diploma	Diploma	Certificate	Integrated	Grand Total
2011-12	81430	34154	3367190	23174950	196159	2071609	184717	74122	29184331
2012-13	95425	30374	3448151	23890309	194072	2207551	191871	94664	30152417
2013-14	107890	31380	3822219	25500325	276502	2285576	187340	125002	32336234
2014-15	117301	33371	3853438	27172346	215372	2507694	170245	141870	34211637
2015-16	126451	42523	3917156	27420450	229559	2549160	144060	155422	34584781
2016-17	141037	43267	4007570	28348197	213051	2612209	166617	173957	35705905
2017-18	161412	34109	4114310	29016350	235263	2707934	177223	195777	36642378
2018-19	169170	30692	4042522	29829075	224711	2699395	162697	241126	37399388
2019-20	202550	23934	4312535	30647287	217249	2672562	159869	300373	38536359
2020-21	211852	16744	4716649	32657509	257187	2979320	155911	385541	41380713
2021-22	212568	26641	5217753	34139233	260475	2916445	184696	460579	43418390
CAGR	8.5	-8.1	12.2	19.1	-7.6	9.4	5.9	9.8	19.9

Sources: Ministry of HRD, Department of Higher Education, 2016, 2021, 2022, GOI.

7. Trend in Programme-wise Enrolment at Under Graduate and Post Graduate Level in Higher Education:

In the higher educational institutions in India the enrolment in various programmes at Under Graduate and Post Graduate level has increased over the years in regular mode of education except in B.Tech., M.Tech., where it has started showing declining trend recently. The estimated enrolment through regular mode of education in important programmes at Under Graduate and Post Graduate levels are shown in the two tables given below (table nos.VII and VIII).

Table No.VII: Programme-wise Enrolment at Under Graduate Level

Enrolment in important programmes at Under Graduate Level in Regular mode of education							
Programme	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2019-20	2021-22
B.A.-Bachelor of Arts	6027027	7898579	9099473	9860520	9651891	9487704	9043884
B.Sc.-Bachelor of Science	2403146	2947052	3579526	4299538	4618172	5092515	4723925
B.Com.-Bachelor of Commerce	2364094	2810308	3117265	3338111	3422312	3666311	3873487
B.Tech.-Bachelor of Technology & B.E.-Bachelor of Engineering	3271286	3775488	4336149	4254919	4203933	3644045	3845332
B.Ed.-Bachelor of Education	436875	509355	559028	657194	514518	1316648	1487090
B.C.A.-Bachelor of Computer Applications	381583	408739	421191	432341	426229	463625	570504
B.B.A.-Bachelor of Business Administration	267375	292838	317024	343237	349667	528740	664621
L.L.B.-Bachelor of Law or Laws	156546	192168	240419	283231	300716	395985	455718
B.Pharm.-Bachelor of Pharmacy	127247	142630	174820	183695	195178	293822	451975
B.Sc.(Nursing)-Bachelor of Science in	126839	156107	176781	179496	191612	289280	399910

Nursing							
M.B.B.S. Bachelor of Medicine and Bachelor of Surgery	110022	144504	160402	170406	191040	287776	320149

Sources: Ministry of HRD, Department of Higher Education, 2016,2020, 2022, GOI.

During the last 10 years, total no. of B. A. enrolment has increased from 6,02,7027 in 2011-12 to 9,04,3884 in 2021-22, M.B.B.S. enrolment has increased from 1,10,022 in 2011-12 to 3,20,149 in 2021-22. The overall growth of M.B.B.S. enrolment is 53%.

During the last 10 years, total no. of M. A. enrolment has increased from 573528 in 2011-12 to 1140462 in 2021-22, M.Sc. enrolment has increased from 377001 in 2011-12 to 834501 in 2021-22. .M.Tech. enrolment has increased from 159561 in 2011-12 to 1,03600 in 2021-22. The growth in enrolment is shown in the table number: VIII.

Table No.VIII: Programme-wise Enrolment at Post Graduate Level in Higher Education

Enrolment in important programmes at Post Graduate Level in Regular mode of Education					
Year	M.A. Master of Arts	M.B.A-Master of Business Administration	M.Com.-Master of Commerce	M.Sc.-Master of Science	M.Tech. - Master of Technology
2011-12	573528	356286	152228	377001	159561
2012-13	662839	392587	179813	414316	209720
2013-14	674447	392937	193373	431723	260370
2014-15	767027	409432	222709	481330	289311
2015-16	878677	416325	271266	519159	257361
2016-17	865410	416490	275695	562896	160888
2017-18	901448	421509	288206	605682	142081

2018-19	899653	462853	321458	623114	135500
2019-20	945895	454459	332481	675217	170692
2021-22	1140462	525989	340253	834501	103600

Sources: Ministry of HRD, Department of Higher Education, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2022, GOI.

8. Reorientation of Higher Education:

Educational opportunities and traditions that Indian universities have built up, since independence have been able to produce graduates, capable only of pursuing limited careers, but, in the new globally competitive environment that is emerging in the country, the Indian student is now required to develop a multifaceted personality to cope up with the rapid changes in the world at large. This calls for the development of body, mind and spirit, through the educational processes in the institutions of higher education. Health consciousness and physical fitness for a healthy body should be an essential part of the university culture. But, a healthy body alone cannot be attained and maintained without a healthy mind. Therefore value education becomes a desirable moral necessity for meeting the challenges of the contemporary world. Professional competence is of little value if professional ethics are forgotten. Similarly, brilliance is of no use if it is employed for anti social activities. In order to achieve all these ends effectively one has to see that the processes of education are properly regulated in terms of assessment and evaluation of learning. In the higher education system in India, UGC has many issues of concern at present, like reorientation of programmes by laying emphasis on health consciousness, values and ethics and quality of higher education together with the assessment of institutions and their accreditation. At present large number of institutions has introduced reorientation of programme like physical education, sports, yoga and recreation activities in the higher education system for the overall good of the younger generation.

9. Challenges in Higher Education in India:

The expansion of higher education system in India has been chaotic and unplanned. The drive to make higher education socially inclusive has led to a sudden and dramatic increase in numbers of institutions without a proportionate increase in material and intellectual resources. As a result, academic standards have been jeopardized. There are many basic problems facing higher education in India today. These include inadequate infrastructure and facilities, large vacancies in faculty positions and poor faculty outmoded

teaching methods, declining research standards, unmotivated students, overcrowded classrooms and widespread geographic, income, gender and ethnic imbalances. There is an inadequate and diminishing financial support for higher education from the government and from society. Many colleges established in rural areas are non-viable, are under enrolled and have extremely poor infrastructure and facilities with just a few teachers. Still we are facing lot of problems and challenges in our education system. Some of the basic challenges in higher education system in India are discussed below:

Enrolment: The Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) of India in higher education is only 15% which is quite low as compared to the developed as well as, other developing countries. With the increase of enrolments at school level, the supply of higher education institutes is insufficient to meet the growing demand in the country.

Equity: There is no equity in GER among different sects of the society. According to previous studies the GER in higher education in India among male and female varies to a greater extent. There are regional variations too some states have high GER while as some is quite behind the national GER which reflect a significant imbalances within the higher education system.

Quality: Quality in higher education is a multi-dimensional, multilevel, and a dynamic concept. Ensuring quality in higher education is amongst the foremost challenges being faced in India today. However, Government is continuously focusing on the quality education. Still Large number of colleges and universities in India are unable to meet the minimum requirements laid down by the UGC and our universities are not in a position to mark its place among the top universities of the world.

Infrastructure: Poor infrastructure is another challenge to the higher education system of India particularly the institutes run by the public sector suffer from poor physical facilities and infrastructure. There are large number of colleges which are functioning on second or third floor of the building on ground or first floor there exists readymade hoseries or photocopy shops.

Political interference: Most of the educational institutions are owned by the political leaders, who are playing key role in governing bodies of the Universities. They are using the innocent students for their selfish means. Students organise campaigns, forget their own objectives and begin to develop their careers in politics.

Faculty: Faculty shortages and the inability of the state educational system to attract and retain well- qualified teachers have been posing challenges to quality education for many years. Large numbers of NET / PhD candidates are unemployed even there are lot of vacancies in higher education, these deserving candidates are then applying in other departments which is a biggest blow to the higher education system.

Accreditation: A total of 13 universities are included in the list of NAAC A++ universities in India which includes Banasthali Vidyapith, Shivaji University, Sri Ramachandra Institute of Higher Education and Research, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, and more.

Moreover enhancing quality of higher education in India would need several interventions. One of them relates to overcoming the shortage of faculty members and improving the quality of existing faculty members. In addition to being strong in their domains and focusing on research, faculty members will need to make learning for students effective. They would also need to make teaching and learning more fun and engaging, contemporary, application based, project based, group work based, etc. To achieve this, they need to update themselves, learn new technologies, use case studies, facilitate group discussions and group activities, organise field trips, negotiate corporate projects, take up community work, etc. They need to take on multiple roles – facilitators for

creating win-win industry-academia partnerships; co-marketeers in their students' projects; co-researchers in their students' field-work; facilitators in start-up incubators, co-founders, and co-investors in their students' entrepreneurial ventures; and promoters, organisers, and coordinators in their students' rock bands, football matches, excursions, yoga and meditation sessions and photography clubs. They would need to have researched the previous night what their students would want to know the next day. They will need to become friends, role models, mentors, and guides to their students. When faculty members are prepared to bring student centricity and all-round development in their approach, we would consider the faculty "energised".

The challenges related to the quality and number of faculty members for Indian HEIs could be divided into **five broad categories**:

1. Attracting foreign faculty to teach in/teach for/research in/research for Indian HEIs
2. Attracting non-faculty within India to become faculty; professors of practice and visiting faculty initiatives to contribute to this initiative
3. Large-scale structured and well-designed faculty training and mentoring programme to equip faculty members with new teaching methodologies, strategies, and techniques; this leads to improved classroom engagement and better student outcomes. These training programmes should strengthen the pedagogical expertise of the faculty and help them focus on making learning for students effective.
4. Providing a platform to unearth excellent faculty members already teaching in India but currently benefitting only a few students (tech-enabled faculty exchange/faculty forum); such platforms should facilitate faculty knowledge exchange and act as connecting platforms designed for collaboration, innovation, communication, and sharing of ideas, resources, and expertise amongst educators. For instance, "Faculty Exchange" forum/hub/forum can be put in place for faculty to share ideas on and contribute to device course content, suggest innovative teaching methods, share experiences of pedagogical challenges faced in the classroom, research findings, etc. To further incentivise and motivate faculty to share their ideas and think of "out-of-the-box" and contemporary solutions to the evolving needs of the education sector, initiatives to recognise and reward ideas could be included.
5. Taking excellent faculty to more students through their e-learning modules and live sessions; this could be through e-learning modules and live virtual classes; scheduled virtual learning hours using videoconferencing tools where participants can ask questions, seek clarification, and have discussions with faculty members; online discussion forums between teachers and students, etc.

The above-mentioned interventions could have a significant impact on the quality of faculty in countries and address the challenge of faculty shortage. This would contribute to enhancing the quality of higher education.

10. Conclusion:

No doubt India is facing various challenges in higher education but to tackle these challenges and to boost higher education is utmost important. India is a country of huge human resource potential, to utilise this potential properly is the issue which needed to discuss. After independence, there has been tremendous increase in institutions of higher learning in all disciplines. But with the quantitative growth has it been able to attend to the core issue of quality. India is today one of the fastest developing countries of the world with the annual growth rate going above 9%. In order to sustain that rate of growth, there is need to increase the number of institutes and also the quality of higher education in India. To reach and achieve the future requirements there is an urgent need to relook at the financial resources, access and equity, quality standards, relevance and at the end the responsiveness.

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